
NASA Lunabotics: Drivetrain

System Requirements Specification

04/20/2025

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Intended Audience

The purpose of this document, the System Requirements Specifications, is to provide a clear and precise description of the functionality and behavior that the Drivetrain of a robot must have. The intended audiences of this document are the leadership, software developers, and hardware engineers at Embry-Riddle's NASA Lunabotics team. This document acts as an agreement between the intended audiences for the requirements of EPIMS.

1.2. Scope of Product

NASA Lunabotics is a competition that challenges teams of university students to design, build, and operate a robotic system in moon-like environment. The teams are tasked to have a robot that is able to navigate through the arena from the starting zone down to the mining zone, mine regolith-simulant, and build a berm in a designated construction zone.

The focus of this document will be the Drivetrain subsystem of the robot that the ERAU's team will be designing for the competition. The drivetrain will be a wheel-based design with a steering mechanism(s) to ensure efficient movement.

1.3. Assumptions, Constraints, Dependencies

- Navigation Computation: The system assumes that the Navigation Computer will handle any navigation errors when in Autonomy mode.
- Hard but unsettled design constraints: The system has a constraint that it needs to have an optimal number of grousers yet no final design of the wheel is possible; some requirements might not have concrete values.
- Connectivity Issues: The system assumes any anomalous data transition from the drivetrain is handled by other subsystems; outside of scope of drivetrain.

1.4. Definitions, Acronyms, and Abbreviations

This section describes definitions, acronyms and abbreviations used throughout this document.

1.4.1. Definitions

This section provides a list of definitions for terms that may be required or helpful for the intended audience.

Table 1: Definitions of terms used

TERM	DEFINITION
Driver	A human that can overtake the controls of the robot from the NaviComputer if needed in case of autonomy issues or failure.
Power Source	An electrical subsystem that distributes and manages the power to all subsystems of the robot
Movement Actuator	An actuator that aids the robot in translation, or forward/backward motion
Rotation Actuator	An actuator that aids the robot in rotation, or steering

1.4.2. Acronyms

This section lists the acronyms used in this document and their associated definitions.

Table 2: Acronyms used

TERM	DEFINITION
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration

1.4.3. Abbreviations

This section lists the abbreviations used in this document and their associated definitions

Table 3: Abbreviations used in the SRS

TERM	DEFINITION
NaviComputer	Navigational Computer - a navigation computer that uses sensors from throughout all of subsystems of the robot to come up with various movement commands autonomously.

1.5. Overview

This System Requirements Specification document contains two main sections: Introduction and Requirement Specifications. The Introduction section presents the purpose of the document, defines the scope of the product, and presents definitions of various acronyms used in this document as well as abbreviations. The second section describes various requirements of the Drivetrain for external interfaces, functional, non-functional and other requirements.

1.6. References

There are no references currently.

2. Specific Requirements

2.1. Functional Requirements

[FR-01] The drivetrain shall enable translational movement to the robot.

[FR-02] The drivetrain shall be able to change the orientation of the robot.

[FR-03] The drivetrain shall output actuator telemetry data.

[FR-04] Each sensor shall measure actuator telemetry data of assigned actuator.

2.2. Non-Functional Requirements

2.2.1. Performance Requirements

[PR-01] The drivetrain shall have a mass no larger than 12.5kg.

[PR-02] The drivetrain shall be capable of speeds of 0 to 0.6 m/s in a straight line.

[PR-03] Telemetry data shall be sent at intervals no greater than 0.5 seconds.

2.2.2. Design Constraints

[DC-01] The drivetrain shall allow the robot to remain within the maximum size of 1.5m x 0.75m x 0.75m.

[DC-02] A wheel shall be able to withstand the weight of up to 37.5 kg

[DC-03] The drivetrain shall be able to withstand stresses from max payload capacity at highest extension of the robot.

[DC-04] The drivetrain shall contain at least one sensor per actuator.

[DC-05] The drivetrain shall consist of 4 wheels.

[DC-06] Each wheel shall have its own movement actuator.

[DC-07] Each wheel shall include grousers, the size and spacing of which shall be optimized to maximize traction on the regolith simulant.

[DC-08] The drivetrain shall include mounting features compatible with 1 in x 1 in aluminum tubes.

[DC-09] The wheels shall be 3-D Printed out of PETG.

[DC-10] The maximum outer diameter of the wheel, measured from grouser tip to grouser tip, shall not exceed 280 mm.

2.2.3. Environmental Requirements

[ER-01] The drivetrain shall have an Ingress Protection rating of IP6X.

[ER-02] The sensors shall utilize sensing methods that do not rely on the fluids or GPS.

[ER-03] The drivetrain shall preserve the physical and chemical properties of the terrain's material.

2.2.4. Reliability Requirements

[RR-01] If the time between last two commands is more than 0.5 seconds, the drivetrain shall set the desired move and rotate commands to zero.

[RR-02] The fasteners securing the drivetrain shall withstand the vibrations generated during drivetrain operation without loosening or failure for the duration of the 15-minute run.

2.2.5. Maintainability Requirements

[MR-01] The drivetrain shall be fastened to the chassis using reusable hardware to support ease of maintenance and disassembly.

2.2.6. Power Requirements

[POW-01] The drivetrain shall use no more than 18 Wh of energy during a 15-minute competition run.

[POW-02] The actuators shall be able to be powered by no more than 24V.

2.3. Interface Requirements

[IR-01] When drivetrain requests power levels, the drivetrain shall send desired level values paired with actuator IDs.

[IR-02] When drivetrain outputs telemetry, the drivetrain shall send the most current state of actuators paired with actuator IDs.

[IR-03] The rotational actuators shall interface with the wheels in a manner that does not impede or conflict with the operation of the movement actuators.

[IR-04] The movement actuators shall interface with the wheels in a manner that does not impede or conflict with the operation of the rotation actuators.

2.4. Behavioral Requirements

[BR-01] The drivetrain shall have Autonomy mode for control.

[BR-02] The drivetrain shall have Manual (Move) mode for control.

[BR-03] The drivetrain shall have Manual (Rotate) mode for control.

[BR-04] The drivetrain shall have Swerve mode for rotation.

[BR-05] The drivetrain shall have Differential mode for rotation.

[BR-06] The drivetrain shall start in Swerve mode for rotation.

[BR-07] The drivetrain shall only have one mode for control at a time.

[BR-08] The drivetrain shall only have one mode for rotation at a time.

[BR-09] When the Autonomy Off command is inputted by the Driver, the drivetrain shall switch to Manual mode in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-10] When initializeSystem command is inputted by the Driver, the drivetrain shall initiate the Autonomy mode in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-11] When rotate command is inputted by NaviComputer and the control mode is Autonomy, the drivetrain shall determine rotation actuator's desired states in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-12] When rotate command is inputted by NaviComputer and the control mode is Autonomy, the drivetrain shall set any simultaneous move command to zero in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-13] When rotation actuator's desired states are determined, the rotation actuators' controllers shall request power levels to rotation actuators in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-14] When move command is inputted by NaviComputer and the control mode is Autonomy, the drivetrain shall determine movement actuators' desired states in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-15] When movement actuators' desired states are determined, the movement actuators' controllers shall request power levels to movement actuators in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-16] When the switch rotation mode command is inputted by Driver and control mode is Manual (Move) or Manual (Rotate), the drivetrain shall switch the rotation mode to Differential in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-17] When joystick state is inputted by Driver and the control mode is Manual (Move), the drivetrain shall determine movement actuator's desired states in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-18] When joystick state is inputted by Driver and the control mode is Manual (Rotation) and the rotation mode is Swerve, the drivetrain shall determine rotation actuator's desired states in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-19] When joystick state is inputted by Driver and the control mode is Manual (Rotation) and the rotation mode is Differential, the drivetrain shall determine movement actuator's desired states in less than 0.2 seconds.

[BR-20] When joystick state is inputted by Driver and the control mode is Autonomy, the drivetrain shall ignore joystick state values.